

of deadhearts and silver shoots.

The data on pests and grain yield for each planting were plotted (see figure). These conclusions were drawn:

1. Stem borer occurrence was below the economic threshold (5%) on crops planted in September and from December to June.

2. Gall midge incidence was low on crops planted from September to January and in May and June.
3. The normal times of planting in the three seasons — September in samba, January in navarai, and June in sornavari — are ideal. Crops yielded higher than average,

12.5 kg/40 m² (3.1 t/ha). Among the three seasons the highest yield was recorded in navarai.

4. In a season, early or late plantings should be accompanied by timely plant protection measures to avoid yield losses to stem borers and gall midges. ■

Minimum insecticide for rice pest control

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Monitoring pest populations on rice and adopting economic thresholds have minimized insecticide spraying in the village of Buddam, Andhra Pradesh.

The average number of sprays before starting an ICORP project was 2.1 sprays in the wet season and 2.7 sprays in the dry season. But when sprays were made only when needed, the average number was reduced to as low as zero sprays in the 1977-78 wet season. Spraying was done only once on 9.72 ha and in the remaining 395 ha a good crop was raised without spraying at all. In general, economic loss due to insect pests was avoided during the period of the project (Table 1). And fewer sprays were made without loss in yield.

Field sample plots provide data to initiate control operations. Plots 0.4 ha in size and representative of varieties and dates of planting are selected, and 5 m² in each provides the area for counting deadhearts at 15, 30, 55 days after transplanting (DT) and silver shoots at

15 and 35 DT. Counts on 50 hills at random provide the data for other pests.

When the pest density or damage is above an economic threshold (Table 2) in a large number of sample plots, a general survey of farmers' fields is undertaken. Insecticide is applied in fields where an economic threshold has been exceeded.

Other benefits also have been noticed. Incidence of pests in general was low, and the onset of incidence was delayed compared to surrounding areas. Predators of brown planthopper and parasites of gall midge and stem borer contributed increasingly to natural control.

In implementing integrated control, economic thresholds were modified in three cases:

1. In the dry season, stem borer attack develops within 15-20 DT. As the crop at this stage has very few tillers, stem borer attack can result in seedling death and gaps in the field. It is desirable to spray insecticide when the damage reaches 5% deadhearts. Deadheart counts must be taken 15, 30, and 55 DT.
2. Brown planthopper large-scale egg laying occurs during favorable climatic conditions in the preflowering and postflowering stages. Nymph density instead of adult

Table 2. Tentative economic thresholds for pest control. Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, Bapatla, India.

Pest	Threshold
Stem borers	10% deadhearts
Gall midge	5% silvershoots
Green leafhopper) Brown leafhopper)	25 insects/hill
Leaffolder	3 damaged leaves/hill
Cutworms) Rice hispa) Grasshoppers)	1 insect/hill

density provides a better basis for control operations. The presence of 25 nymphs/hill was found to be a useful economic threshold.

3. Since it is difficult to locate the climbing cutworm caterpillars, a better indicator than density is cut panicles. The presence of 5 cut panicles/m² should be the threshold for insecticidal spraying. ■

Effect of volume of insecticide spray on brown planthopper mortality

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Reducing the volume of water in insecticide spray minimizes the cost of farm labor to carry water to the area of application. To determine whether insecticide toxicity is affected by spray volumes, 250, 500, and 1,000 liters insecticide solutions/ha were sprayed on 30- to 35-day-old TN1 potted plants at a rate of 0.75 kg ai/ha using an atomizer run by an air compressor. Beginning one day after treatment (DAT) 20 female adult brown planthoppers were caged on treated plants at 5-day intervals. Insect mortality was recorded 48 hours after caging.

Table 1. Effect of insecticide sprays on rice yield in Bapatla, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Year	Wet season				Dry season			
	ICORP village		Control village		ICORP village		Control village	
	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)
1974-75 ^a	2.1	4.23	2.8	3.57	2.7	3.15	3.2	3.33
1975-76	1.4	3.75	2.1	2.53	0.7	4.50	3.1	4.40
1976-77	0.3	5.00	0.2	3.33	0.3	4.18	2.3	4.19
1977-78	0.0	4.60 ^b 1.77 ^c	0.2	2.65	1.5	3.52	1.6	3.18
1978-79	0.1	4.01	0.4	3.65	—	—	—	—
1979-80	0.3	4.20	0.5	4.00	—	—	—	—

^aBase year. ^bYield before a cyclone. ^cYield after a cyclone.

Effect of spray volume (0.75 kg a.i./ha) on mortality of brown planthoppers. IRRI insectary, 1980.

Insecticide and volume (liters/ha)	Mortality ^a (%)				
	1 DAT	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT	20 DAT
Carbofuran 12 F					
1000	100 a	98 a	90 a	62 a	20 a
500	100 a	99 a	92 a	68 a	27 a
250	94 a	36 b	14 b	9 b	0 b
Perthane 45 EC					
1000	100 a	98 a	41 a	16 ab	2 a
500	98 a	84 a	39 a	30 a	8 a
250	100 a	93 a	39 a	7 b	0 a
Monocrotophos 30 EC					
1000	94 ab	32 a	10 a	7 a	2 a
500	95 a	28 a	7 a	3 a	2 a
250	83 b	26 a	0 a	2 a	0 a
UC54229 100 Tech.					
1000	99 a	100 a	91 a	55 a	25 a
500	100 a	99 a	82 a	42 ab	9 a
250	98 a	82 b	58 b	23 b	5 a

^aAdjusted using Abbott's formula. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DAT = days after treatment.

Mortality for three volumes of Perthane and monocrotophos spray was similar (see table). However, carbofuran and UC54229 usually were most toxic when applied at 1,000 and 500 liters. ■

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Soil and crop management

Effects of phosphorus fertilizer sources in calcareous soil

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A field experiment on calcareous silty clay soil (pH 7.7, OM 0.4% Ca 23.0 meq/100 g, Mg 13.0 meq/ 100 g, CEC 15 meq/100 g, and Olsen P 4.2 ppm) evaluated two sources of phosphate fertilizer: diammonium phosphate (DAP) and triple superphosphate (TSP). Urea was applied as a nitrogen source with TSP.

Fertilizer treatments were randomized in a complete block design with four

Effect of sources of phosphate fertilizer on plant height, tiller number, plant phosphorus concentration 30 days after transplanting, and grain yield of rice in calcareous soil in Malaysia.^a

Source of P fertilizer ^b	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	P concentration (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
None (control)	25 c	18 c	0.15 c	3.0 c
DAP	38 b	34 b	0.17 b	4.5 b
TSP	45 a	39 a	0.18 a	5.1 a
CV %	3.61	3.02	1.41	2.97

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bControl = 120 kg N/ha and no P, DAP = diammonium phosphate, TSP = triple superphosphate + urea.

replications. Nitrogen and phosphorus levels were 120 kg N/ha and 60 kg P₂O₅/ha. All of the P and half the N were broadcast and incorporated into the soil two days before IR6 seedlings were transplanted. The remaining N was topdressed at the time of panicle

initiation.

The number of tillers per hill, plant height, percent plant P concentration at 30 days after transplanting (DT), and grain yield increased significantly with the combination of urea and TSP (see table). ■

Rice germination and seedling response to oxygen in floodwater

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Germination and establishment of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) seedlings are usually less than optimum in water-saturated and flooded soils, apparently because of

a deficiency of available oxygen (O₂). This study evaluated the effect of specific O₂ levels on seedling development and identified rice cultivars that may be more tolerant of the low O₂ concentrations associated with water-saturated rice soils.

Gas flowmeters and regulators allow mixing of air and N₂ gas. Six O₂ levels — 21, 10.5, 5.3, 2.0, 1.0, and 0% (99.995% N₂ gas) — were bubbled into a transparent plastic box (36 × 28 × 9 cm deep) holding deionized water 7.5 cm

deep. Seeds of 4 rice cultivars were suspended on cheesecloth about 3 cm below the water surface. As gas of desired O₂ concentration dispersed into the box, the water circulated slowly. Water circulation plus a thin transparent polyethylene cover helped assure that O₂ concentration within each box was uniform. A YSI Model 53 O₂ meter monitored O₂ levels continuously. Seed boxes were placed in a growth chamber providing light intensity of 400 microeinsteins/m² per second, a 12-hour day,